

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ARUNSHIKA: A SINGLE CASE STUDY**Vd. Akshara Vikas Suryawanshi¹, Vd. Omkar Kortikar²**¹PG Scholar Kayachikitsa Department Siddhakala Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya, Sangamner.²HOD and Guide Kayachikitsa Department Siddhakala Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya Sangamner.***Corresponding Author: Vd. Akshara Vikas Suryawanshi**

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ABSTRACT

Arunshika" is described in Ayurvedic texts as a Shirogat Roga (disease affecting the head). It is a type of Kshudra Roga (minor disease), primarily affecting the scalp and closely resembles conditions like carbuncle or folliculitis on the head in modern terms. In Ayurveda it is caused by Kapha-Pitta vitiation, Rakta dhatu, krumi leading to inflammatory swelling, pus formation, itching and appears like mustard seed. A 26 year old male patient came in OPD for complaint of boil, pain, itching, redness and pus discharged at scalp since 15 -20 days. The line of Treatment given to patient kapha pitta shamak, rakta shodhak and pitta rechak. Good result observed after 15 days of treatment. This kind of approach may be taken into consideration for further treatment and research work of Arunshika.

KEYWORD: Arunshika, Shirogat Roga, Kshudra Roga, Krumi, Carbuncle, Folliculitis.**INTRODUCTION**

Acharya Sushruta Chakradutta and Bhavprakash have mentioned Arunshika in Kshudraroga^[1] (minor diseases). Acharya Vagbhat and Sharangdhara describe in Shirogat roga under caption of Urdhvajatrugat rog and further divided into nine Kapalgat rog. According to Acharya Vagbhat in Uttar tantra Vitiated pitta and kapha along with Rakta Dhatu and krumi reaches to shirpradesh and twacha (scalp) get affected leading to Arunshika.^[2] This skin conditions are seen as a result of a changed lifestyle, inadequate exercise, poor hygiene, emotional stress, and bad eating habits it's causes imbalance of dosha in body. It also seen due to over used of shampoo, hair gel, and hair colouring agent leading to scalp damaged It's creates excessive dryness and clogged pores over scalp.

CASE STUDY

A 26-year-old male presented with Chief Complaints – Pain, itching and pus discharge over scalp.
History of Present illness - Approximately Fifteen to twenty days back patient develops.

Small boil on scalp and having pain and itching, after 4-5 days it becomes reddish, Whitish discoloration pus formation occurs.

History of past medication - History of Amlapitta.

Personal History - There was no personal history of any major disease like HTN, Diabetes, endocrinal disorder.

Surgical History - history of appendectomy before 15 year.

General Examination

- Blood pressure – 120/80 mmHg
- Pulse – 70/min
- Respiratory rate – 18/min
- P/A – Soft
- Weight – 55 kg

Ashtavidha Pariksha

- Nadi - Vata pittaj
- Mala - Once a day
- Mutra - frequency – 5-6 times a day, normal colour (pale yellow)
- Jihwa - Niram
- Shabda - Speech and hearing was normal

- Sparsha - Anushna
- Drik - Normal
- Aakriti - Madyama

Roga Prikshan

- Hetu - Aharaja - Intake of oily, Lavana, sweet food, and dairy products, Virudha ahar
Viharaja – Exposure to Heat.
- Poorvaroopā –Pidika(Boil on scalp)
- Roopā – Pidika, Vedana (Pain), Kandu(itching), Raag (Redness), puy utpatti (Pus formation)

- Upashaya – Ushnasupachya Ahara.
- Samprati -In this patient due to pitta pradhan (dominant) kapha Dushti (vitiation), Rakta dhatu and Twacha get affected, leading to inflammatory swelling, pus formation.

Local Examination - Boil On Scalp

Moist in nature, Red in colour. The thickness varies between 2 and 3 mm.

Treatment Given.

Medicine	Dose	Route
Raktapachak Vati	250 mg BD After Food	Oral
Arogyavardini Vati	250 mg BD After Food	Oral
Gandhak rasayan	250 mg BD After Food	Oral
Krumi kuthar ras	250 mg BD After Food	Oral
Nimb Tail	TDS	Local

Diet for Patient

Avoid excess salt in diet and Excessive spices.

Avoid dairy products

Avoid virudha Aahar such as milk with fruit and milk with fish.

Eat freshly cook, Light food.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Following observations are seen during treatment given to patient result.

Symptoms	0 th day	F/U after 7 th days of treatment	F/U after 15 th days of treatment
Vedana (Pain)	+++	-	-
Kandu (Itching)	+++	+	-
Raag (Redness)	++++	++	-
Puya Srav (Pus discharged)	++	-	-

RESULT

After 7 days of treatment Pain and pus formation subsided and Itching and Redness over boil significantly

reduced. And after 15th days of treatment all symptoms are completely reduced.

Before Treatment

After Treatment

DISCUSSION

In this case, the patient presented with clinical features consistent with Arunshika, described in Ayurvedic texts as a Pitta-Kapha predominant condition characterized by

painful, red, inflamed swellings resembling modern-day boils or furuncles.^[3] The therapeutic approach focused on correcting the underlying dosha imbalance specifically the vitiation of Pitta and Kapha. The selected medicines

possess proven Dosha Shamak, Krimighna (antimicrobial), Raktashodhaka (blood purifier), and Vrana Ropaka (wound healing) properties. Remarkably, the patient achieved 100% relief within two weeks of treatment, with complete resolution of swelling, pain, pus discharge, and erythema. No recurrence or complications were observed during the one-month follow-up period. This outcome strongly supports the efficacy of classical Ayurvedic formulations in managing Arunshika, particularly in cases where antibiotic resistance or recurrence is a concern in modern medicine.

CONCLUSION

Arunshika Vyadhi, though chronic and recurrent in nature, can be successfully treated with Ayurvedic principles. This case showed 100% clinical success without modern antibiotics or steroids. More clinical trials and documentation can help establish standardized Ayurvedic protocols for follicular skin conditions.

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